

The impact of capital markets on economic development in countries

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Abstract The role of capital markets in the global economy is evolving with increasing financial innovation. This paper offers a complete assessment of the work done so far in order to evaluate the role of capital markets in establishing a safe and sustainable world and builds a research framework for examining the connection between financing and sustainable development on the basis of the review. The paper presents empirical data and underlines the critical questions that political decision makers, scientists, practitioners, global financial institutions for development and other players need to address. The study culminates with the development of important investigation gaps.

Keywords: Sustainable development, Capital market, finance, sustainability, Responsible investing, Corporate social responsibility, Socially responsible property investments

Introduction

It is now more familiar at domestic and international level with the capital market, equities and bonds. Increasing numbers of consumers and businessmen, including governments, aim to boost revenues by investing in short or long-term stocks and bonds. In addition, young people nowadays want to increase revenues through the purchase and sale of shares on the financial market.

The capital market is a site of trading in assets such as shares, bonds, currencies and derivatives¹ for buyers and sellers. In general, finance markets are

characterized by clear pricing, fundamental rules on trading, expenses and charges and market forces which determine the values of the trade securities¹.

Currently, practically any nation, at varying stages and transaction volumes, can readily find capital markets. Some financial markets are still in development while billions of dollars are trading on a daily basis in other nations such as the United States of America, where there are the New York Stock Exchange and Forex markets.

The value of money and prices in the capital markets is generated by most tradable financial instruments. If the economy goes well and demand is stronger, prices may be higher than historical levels and income greater. Nevertheless, macroeconomic variables may cause the price of tradeable instruments to decrease when the levels of taxes change, national output decreases or level of employment, which may lead to a decrease in the returns of investors.

The study intends to examine if the capital market plays a role and how in a country's economic and social life. At the outset, the author begins to explain the capital market, its brief history and how it is functioning now. The author then proceeds to study the major financial indicators that reflect a country's wealth and degree of economic and social life using a public domestic and international database offered by well-known authorities. The research showed that a robust capital market may lead to a country's whole economic and social growth.

Literature Review The inquiry began with capital market history. For this purpose, the study looked back on the past and attempted to find out what makes this type of market part of economic life from ancient materials, articles, books and statistics. Later on statistics from the world's major capital markets will be used to

¹ Eugene, F., Brigham, Joel, F., Houston. (2016). *Fundamental of Financial Management*, South-Western College Pub.

indicate their influence on money movement and business on the economy and on social matters.

The statistical data on public websites from the main capital markets of the world and public finance institutions will be used.

Research shows that Europe begins with the first sort of capital market. Just as there were always persons in every area of the earth who had financing resources and others who sought. In Europe, private lenders filled significant voids created by giant banks. Intermediaries arrived at that time and tried to cover the company's obligations. In the 1300s, Venetians (Italy) were leaders in the area and began trading securities in and across nations.

The New York Bond was formally established in 1792 in New York². Because the London Börse was hamstrung by the restrictive regulations, the New York Börse has been inhabited by commercial stocks since the start. However, the glory goes to the Philadelphia Stock Exchange and swiftly becomes the most dominant. NYSE is not the first bond exchange in the US. New York Stock Exchange was founded on Wall Street, and was founded by brokers. More than anything else, the location aspects led to the prevailing position of NYSE. It was at the center of all trade and businesses from and to the US and for most banks and large enterprises. The New York Stock Exchange became a highly rich institution through establishing demanding printing demands and orders.

The London Stock Exchange works worldwide as Europe's premier exchange, but is still the largest multinational firm listed on the New York Stock Exchange.

Today, a number of developed countries, including Switzerland, Germany, France, Japan, Australia, Canada, the UAE and Saudi Arabia, created their own

² Philadelphia Stock Exchange (PHLX), now known as NASDAQ OMX PHLX, is the oldest stock exchange in the United States, founded in 1790. It is now owned by The NASDAQ OMX Group. Source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Philadelphia_Stock_Exchange.

bourses, but these were largely considered proof of the domestic companies' ability to live until they were prepared to take a step towards the London Bond and from there on to the New York Stock Exchange's large leagues.

Financial Markets Nowadays Contemporary economists argue that development of the capital market is also supported by international financial institutions to reduce dependence on the foreign financing and banking sector, and therefore, because the capital market financing costs are significantly lower than institutional finance (Andrei Radulescu—Capital Market Journal Interview)³. Our research showed that there is a developed economic and social level, sustainable economic growth, low risk in the nations with trillions of dollars being traded and/or other international currencies, such as British English, Euro or Japanese Yen.

The research shows that in the present time the biggest capital markets in the world are located in the most developed countries such as: USA (New York Stock Exchange and NASDAQ—both in New York), United Kingdom (London Stock Exchange Group—London), Japan (Japan Exchange Group—Tokyo), and China (Shanghai Stock Exchange). Table 1 presents the first 10 biggest capital markets in the world, according to the trade monthly volume. capital markets participate actively to the economic and social countries level development. In USA, the share of public and private business which is financed through capital market is much higher compared with other countries from Asia and Europe.

In order to investigate the influence of capital markets on countries economic life, it was chosen some important indicators. Based on the available data and on what it was the purpose of the investigation, it was also indicated to take into consideration of lagging indicators (which reflect the economy's historical

³Andrei Rădulescu, Senior Economist at Transilvania Bank, Moldova Republic. <http://capital.market.md/ro/content/andrei-radulescu-dezvoltarea-pietei-de-capital-poate-dinamiza-economia-moldovei>.

performance and changes to these are only identifiable after an economic trend or pattern has already been established) and leading indicators (which often change prior to large economic adjustments and, as such, can be used to predict future trends). The research used database such as: Eurostat, central banks, International Monetary Fund, World Bank, BMI Research, website of domestic ministries of finance, and/or economy. Thus because, it wanted to proof that capital markets help economies, investments, and economic growth. Therefore, there were created three categories: countries with a strong capital market activity (United States, United Kingdom, Germany, and France) using conventional finance system; countries with a strong capital market activity (United Arab Emirates and Saudi Arabia) using Islamic finance system; and emergent countries where capital markets are at an incipient level (Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Romania, and Spain).

Table 1

Major Stock Exchanges (Top 20 by Market Capitalization) of Issued Shares of Domestic Companies, as of 31 January 2015 (Monthly Reports, World Federation of Exchanges)

				(USD bn)	
New York stock exchange	United States	New York	19,223	1,520	-5
NASDAQ	United States	New York	6,831	1,183	-5
London stock exchange group	United Kingdom	London	6,187	165	+0
	Italy				
Japan exchange group—Tokyo	Japan	Tokyo	4,485	402	+9
Shanghai stock exchange	China	Shanghai	3,986	1,278	+8
Dubai financial market	United Arab	Dubai	xx	3,392.90	0.91
Hong Kong stock exchange	Hong Kong	Hong Kong	3,325	155	+8
		Amsterdam			
		Brussels			
Euronext	European Union	Lisbon	3,321	184	+1
		London			
		Paris			
Shenzhen stock exchange	China	Shenzhen	2,285	800	+8
TMX group	Canada	Toronto	1,939	120	-5
Deutsche Börse	Germany	Frankfurt	1,762	142	+1
Bombay stock exchange	India	Mumbai	1,682	11.8	+5.5

National stock exchange of India	India	Mumbai	1,642	62.2	+5.5
SIX Swiss exchange	Switzerland	Zurich	1,516	126	+1
Australian securities exchange	Australia	Sydney	1,272	55.8	+10
Korea exchange	South Korea	Seoul	1,251	136	+9
OMX Nordic exchange	Northern Europe, Armenia	Stockholm	1,212	63.2	various
JSE limited	South Africa	Johannesburg	951	27.6	+2
BME Spanish exchanges	Spain	Madrid	942	94.0	+1
Taiwan stock exchange	Taiwan	Taipei	861	54.3	+8
BM&F Bovespa	Brazil	São Paulo	824	51.1	-3
Saudi stock exchange (Tadawul)	Saudi Arabia	Riyadh	...	21.32	+4

It is understandable that in any country's economic existence, capital markets play a very essential role. It is required to quickly outline the most renowned financial organizations and instruments on capital markets before beginning to highlight this relevance in the perspective of economic indicators.

It is understandable that in any country's economic existence, capital markets play a very essential role. It is required to quickly outline the most renowned financial organizations and instruments on capital markets before beginning to highlight this relevance in the perspective of economic indicators. Basically, financial instruments, the acquisition and marketing of inventories and bonds, gold, foreign currencies, oil or other items or services of economic worth may be used by any form of financial organization. However: stock, bonds, bills or bills, foreign moneys, gold, silver and oil and other by-products, are the most traded financial items. It can readily be noticed that any market in which buyers and sellers engage in the trade in assets such as shares, bonds, currencies and derivatives is a broad phrase. Capital markets are normally determined by clear pricing, basic trading restrictions, expenses and charges and a determination by market forces of securities prices. In almost every country in the globe, capital markets can now be found. Some are relatively tiny and only a few participants, others are trading trillion dollars a day, such as the New York Stock Exchange

(NYSE)⁴ Conclusions Capital, financial instruments and operating systems are presently quite complicated and are being used to encourage the growth of the real economy in the interests of the capital market participants as a means of quality intermediation, financial supervision and players in the sophisticated game.

Capital markets have become the national and world economies' arbitrators and judges in the last decades. In fact, the market does not ignore anything: domestic macroeconomic performance reflects the capital market; government economic (fiscal, financial, monetary and social) policies are measured on stock and bond markets; state and private companies are often judged by trading stocks and bonds on financial markets.

Analyses have shown that capital markets exist and work properly to support social and economic growth and contribute to a higher trust level for investors and a greater prestige compared to other countries. The accuracy of financial data and legislative stability may be relied upon by business people. However, if there is no political, social, and economic stability, capital markets cannot be formed.

In order to enhance its economic level, maintain balance of payment and preserve economic and social stability, developed economies employ capital markets. In developing or emerging economies the balance of payments or the expansion of productive capabilities, as well as the raising and maintenance of social stability levels, have continuously resorted to capital markets.

In the case of emerging economies, the creation and evolution of capital markets involve or involves a financial system reform process that adapts to investor demands and adopted new standards for the extent of internal powers and in accordance with integration requirements in a regional or international context, insurance policies and the preservation of economic and monetary stability.

⁴ <http://www.investopedia.com/walkthrough/corporate-finance/1/financial-markets.aspx>

Finally, capital markets truly help the growth of countries by bringing together investors, people and governments that have or need money. Therefore, capital markets are actively involved in the development and construction of a sustainable economy.

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